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Automated particle counting app in liquid medium based on digital image processing

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ABSTRACT: This work introduces the mobile app ContLab with advanced computational code installed on mobile devices (tablet, cellphone, iPad, etc.), with internet access, and compatible with Android operating systems. It is designed to be coupled with a simple microscope for the automated counting of particles, ranging in size from 0.05 μm to 50 μm , within the microfiltration spectrum, and specifically customized for micelle counting produced in fermentable processes. It is an easily accessible and cost-effective device for users interested in micelle counting present in any fermentable broth, such as in the pharmaceutical, food, and brewing industries. The app enhances the speed and precision of results compared to the manual counting method.

Keywords: App; Computer Vision; Counting; Particles; Micelles.

1. INTRODUCTION

The particle counting in liquid media is crucial task in various fields, for example the pharmaceutical industry, environmental science, and research. Several techniques are employed for this purpose, each with its advantages and limitations [1,2]. A common approach is optical microscopy, where suspended particles are visualized under a microscope [3]. Manual counting can be performed, but there are also automatic techniques, such as image-based counting, using computational algorithms to identify and quantify the particles [4]. Another widely used technique is light scattering analysis, known as flow cytometry. In this method, suspended particles are passed through a laser beam, and light dispersion is measured at different angles. This provides information about the size and complexity of the particles, allowing for the counting and characterization of heterogeneous populations [5].

Furthermore, the electrical impedance technique is employed for counting suspended particles. In this method, an electric field is applied to a counting cell, and the moving particles generate electrical signals proportional to their volume. Analysis of these signals enables the determination of the number and size of particles present in the liquid medium. These techniques have a crucial function in various applications, contributing to quality control, scientific research, and environmental monitoring [6]. In the pharmaceutical industry, for example, accurate particle counting is essential.

The drug recovery process is essential for development and large-scale production. In the downstream stage, microfiltration is often employed to separate unwanted particles and impurities from the final product.

The efficiency of this process is vital to ensure the purity and quality of the drugs [7]. Accurate counting of the number of particles in the liquid medium during microfiltration is essential aspect to evaluate the performance of this stage [8]. This allows for monitoring the effectiveness of particle removal, optimizing operating conditions, and ensuring that the final product meets the rigorous quality standards required by the pharmaceutical industry.

In the microfiltration process, the term micelle is used instead particle due to the presence of compound aggregates in the fermentable medium. These micelles represent complex structures formed by associating molecules, for example lipids, sugars and proteins, and can be efficiently separated during microfiltration [9]. The use of the term micelles emphasizes the colloidal nature of these particles, highlighting the importance of their removal to ensure the purity and quality of the final product. In this context, the Neubauer chamber is a fundamental tool in manual particle counting in liquid media, utilized by researchers across various fields. Its significance lies in its ability to provide an accurate and reliable measurement of particles number in a sample. Despite to a manual method that requires more time compared to automated techniques such as flow cytometry, the Neubauer chamber is a cost-effective and economically viable option for many laboratories [10]. Its simplicity and reduced cost make it a popular choice, especially in research settings where accuracy in particle counting is crucial, and resource availability may be limited [11]. Thus, the Neubauer chamber continues to satisfy a significant role in the manual analysis of particles in liquid media, offering an accessible and effective approach for researchers.

Automated particle counting equipment often comes with a high cost, posing a financial challenge for laboratories and researchers, especially in contexts with more constrained budgets. In contrast, the Neubauer chamber provides a cheaper manual option. A viable solution to overcome this financial barrier could be the development of specialized mobile applications that could be integrated with microscopes, enabling automated particle counting [12, 13]. This approach would leverage widely available mobile technology, offering more accessible and efficient alternative for particle counting compared to traditional equipment. This innovation could democratize access to particle counting technology, making it more available to a variety of laboratories and researchers, contributing to resource efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

In this context, this work presents the mobile app ContLab, equipped with sophisticated computational code, designed for mobile devices for example tablets and smartphones. The app requires internet access, and it is compatible with both Android operating systems. It is designed for use alongside a basic microscope to automatically identify particles ranging from 0.05 μm to 50 μm , in the microfiltration range.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Microfiltration

This research was conducted at the Department of Process Engineering (DEPro), School of Chemical Engineering (FEQ), University of Campinas (UNICAMP). The fermented broth subjected to microfiltration was produced by Bertan, Silva, and Cremasco [14] to produce the drug tacrolimus, mainly used in the treatment of transplant recipients [15], dermatological diseases [16], and ocular conditions [17]. The fermented broth was submitted to microfiltration, where impurities are removed, resulting in permeate ready for subsequent processes. Membranes with different pore sizes, including 0.22 μm and 3.00 μm , and controlled operational pressures of 1 and 2 bar, were employed in the process. Micelle counting was performed on both the fermented broth and the permeate to assess the microfiltration process efficiency. An optimized approach was adopted,

involving recirculation of the crude broth through the same membrane under controlled pressure. The repetition of this cycle, up to ten times, was implemented to enhance the retention of micelles present in the liquid.

2.2. Samples

The samples of fermented broth and permeate obtained from microfiltration were stored in amber glass bottles and refrigerated in a refrigerator (Electrolux, DC35A) at temperatures ranging from 1.7 °C to 3.3 °C. The samples were homogenized using an orbital shaker (Criemaq, C200) at 110 rpm for 1 minute. Subsequently, 5 mL of the homogenized sample were collected and placed in a 10 mL test tube for the subsequent micelle counting.

2.3. Counting chamber

The Fuchs Rosenthal counting chamber (Kasvi, K5-0127) was sterilized with 70% ethanol and placed on the stage of the optical microscope (YEGREN, XSP-ZJ2054). A 10 μ L sample was collected, and the uniformity of sample absorption between the Neubauer chamber and the glass slide was then verified. This procedure ensured a homogeneous distribution of the sample, providing optimal conditions for analysis.

2.4. ContLab

The application was built using the open-source React Native framework, which leverages the open-source NodeJS technology. NodeJS, in turn, communicates with a web processing layer in a back end using the open-source Flask framework, with computer vision libraries OpenCV and scikit-learn. The entire web layer is programmed in Python. To enable the functionality of the image processing code, images are captured by devices for example the built-in camera in a mobile device (cellphone), attached to a simple microscope, and sent for particle counting arranged on a Neubauer chamber or glass slide (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. System for automated particle counting.

The application offers two user input methods. In the first input option, the user selects “number of particles/area”, and in the second input option, the user selects “number of particles/volume”. Anyway, of the input, the user takes a photograph or chooses an image file from the device itself, i.e., image acquisition is carried out through the mobile device camera attached to the optical microscope or by uploading an image file from the device memory. Then, the user selects the counting area using the “crop” tool. It is recommended that the grid cropping be external, meaning that the sent image still retains the white borders of the counting area. The choice between the number of particles/area or particle/volume depends on the user's specific objectives.

The images were captured with a resolution of 1280 by 1024 pixels in JPG (Joint Photographic Experts Group) format using the Galaxy A01 mobile phone (Samsung, SM-A015M/DS). For a better understanding of the steps required to execute the ContLab analysis, the operational flowchart of ContLab is illustrated in Fig. 2, and in Fig. 3, an illustration of the installation and operation of the application is provided. The analysis imposes no restrictions on the model of the mobile device, allowing the use of various devices. The versatility in this regard enhances the accessibility and practicality of the analysis in different environments.

Figure 2. Layout of the operation screens of ContLab.

Figure 3. Application installed and operating on the mobile phone.

The algorithm consists of several image processing steps as depicted in the block diagram in Fig. 4 as:

- a) To receive the image in base 64 bits in the body of a HTTP request made in the Contlab app and convert it to a file manipulable by the OpenCV library.
- b) To adjust the image to the size of 800 pixels by 800 pixels, standardizing the rest of the algorithm.
- c) To convert to the grayscale color scale for the execution of the multi-Otsu threshold image processing algorithm. That thresholding, when performed in different configurations, aims to mitigate the effects of variations in brightness and color in the photograph.
- d) To perform the multi-Otsu threshold algorithm with 3 classes (dividing the image into 3 sectors of different colors), resulting in a matrix with the numbers 0, 1, and 2.
- e) To perform the multi-Otsu threshold algorithm with 4 classes (dividing the image into 4 sectors of different colors), resulting in a matrix with the numbers 0, 1, 2, and 3.
- f) To perform the multi-Otsu threshold algorithm with 5 classes (dividing the image into 4 sectors of different colors), resulting in a matrix with the numbers 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4.
- g) To divide the grid into 16 matrices, each containing one of the smaller areas.
- h) To remove from each of the 16 matrices, the areas identified as particles (micelles) that, under the experimental conditions, should preferably be in darker colors than the rest of the sample, corresponding to the numbers 2, 3, and 4 in the multi-Otsu threshold algorithms of 3, 4, and 5 classes, respectively.
- i) To count the identified contours in each of the 3 variations of the 16 grid areas.
- j) To calculate the average between particle counting in each of these variations.
- k) To sum the counting from each of the 16 grid areas.
- l) Return the information on particle counting in each sector of the grid and the final counting.
- m) Send the final counting to ContLab app.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Commonly, the quantitative calculation of particles after downstream processes, for example microfiltration, is neglected, presuming that all micelles have been retained in the membranes [18, 19, 20]. This study highlights the significance of counting the micelles present in the permeate and crude broth, providing a more accurate approach to evaluating the effectiveness of micelle retention and, consequently, enhancing the quality of the material for the subsequent downstream stage.

Figure 4. Block diagram of the overall algorithm procedure.

The use of the Neubauer chamber for counting micelles in fermentable broths represents a significant innovation. In hematology, the Neubauer chamber is widely employed for counting blood cells, such as erythrocytes and leukocytes, providing crucial information for the diagnosis and monitoring of hematological conditions [21]. In biological research, the Neubauer chamber is utilized for cell counting in cultures, enabling precise assessments of cell density and viability in cell proliferation studies [22]. In microbiology, the Neubauer chamber is applied to count bacteria and other microorganisms in liquid samples, aiding in the determination of concentration and viability in microbiological cultures [23].

The development of a user-friendly and quickly yielding app like ContLab proves to be central in this context, enabling a more efficient analysis and prompt decision-making to optimize processes. Considering that a more effective separation of micelles directly contributes to the improvement of the final product quality. The ContLab app can be tested for the counting of other particles within the same microfiltration separation range and at the upper limit of ultrafiltration (0.05 μm to 50 μm), for example pigments, blood cells, emulsified oils, fat micelles, activated carbon, among other particles present in liquid media.

One of the recurrent challenges in capturing a complete image of the Neubauer chamber is the distortion of the boundaries, making it difficult to achieve focus and a sharply defined image [24, 25]. In studies involving the microscopy of biological cells, irregularities at the sample edges can lead to limitations in the automatic segmentation of particles, resulting in inaccurate counting [26]. This distortion may stem from sample preparation objects, contrast variations, or natural deformations in the objects under analysis. Confronting these challenges requires advanced image processing approaches to compensate for distortions and enhance counting

accuracy [27]. The presence of noise or imperfections in captured images can complicate the task of automatically identifying and counting particles. ContLab reports and resolves this issue by utilizing multiple uncompressed images (Raw format) to improve image interpretation. In this format, the image undergoes no pre-processing treatments.

In Tables 1 up to 4, with respective Figures 5 up to 8, are presented the results of micelle counting for different microfiltered samples of crude broth produced at the Laboratory of Process and Mass Transfer/LPTM/FEQ/UNICAMP. Manual micelle counting was based on the study by Bertan [28].

Table 1. Micelle counting from the MF test with 0.22 μm membrane at 1 bar.

Microfiltration steps	Manual counting (Number of micelles/ mm^3)	ContLab app (Number of micelles/ mm^3)	Improvement in counting (Number of micelles/ mm^3)
1	99	112	13
2	57	67	10
3	21	39	18
4	19	27	8
5	17	19	2
6	10	16	6
7	7	11	4
8	8	9	1
9	4	6	2
10	5	6	1

Figure 5. Comparison between manual particle counting and ContLab app for multistep microfiltration conditions at 1 bar using a 0.22 μm membrane.

Table 2. Micelle counting from the MF test with 0.22 μm membrane at 2 bar.

Microfiltration steps	Manual counting (Number of micelles/ mm^3)	ContLab app (Number of micelles/ mm^3)	Improvement in counting (Number of micelles/ mm^3)
1	129	138	9
2	112	121	9
3	100	113	13
4	82	98	16
5	77	86	9
6	61	75	14
7	59	64	5
8	39	49	10
9	22	37	15
10	9	12	3

Figure 6. Comparison between manual particle counting and ContLab app for multistep microfiltration conditions at 2 bar using a 0.22 μm membrane.

Table 3. Micelle counting from the MF test with 3.00 μm membrane at 1 bar.

Microfiltration steps	Manual counting (Number of micelles/mm ³)	ContLab app (Number of micelles/mm ³)	Improvement in counting (Number of micelles/mm ³)
1	101	116	15
2	57	72	15
3	11	21	10
4	19	34	15
5	14	26	12
6	12	18	6
7	9	13	4
8	4	10	6
9	4	9	5
10	4	6	2

Figure 7. Comparison between manual particle counting and ContLab app for multistep microfiltration conditions at 1 bar using a 3.00 μm membrane.

Table 4. Micelle counting from the MF test with 3.00 μm membrane at 2 bar.

Microfiltration steps	Manual counting (Number of micelles/mm ³)	ContLab app (Number of micelles/mm ³)	Improvement in counting (Number of micelles/mm ³)
1	133	147	14
2	110	132	22
3	110	129	19
4	83	119	36
5	80	86	6
6	62	77	15
7	59	65	6
8	36	39	3
9	11	24	13
10	9	16	7

Figure 8. Comparison between manual particle counting and ContLab app for multistep microfiltration conditions at 2 bar using a 3.00 μm membrane.

It is possible to observe in Tables 1 up to 4, the improvement in counting with ContLab approach. Besides the inspection of Figs. 5 up to 8, this improvement can be while relative mean deviation (RMD), defined as

$$RMD(\%) = \left(\frac{PC_{ContLab} - PC_{Manual}}{PC_{Manual}} \right) \times 100 \tag{1}$$

with PC is number of particle/mm³, and the subscripts ContLab and Manual are associated with ContLab and manual counting respectively. RMD represents the percentage difference between the automated counting by ContLab and the manual counting. A higher relative mean deviation indicates a greater level of disparity between these two counting methods. In this context, the relative mean deviation was notably higher in the 3.00 μm membrane and at a pressure of 1 bar (64.47 %), indicating greater variability in these conditions. ContLab demonstrates an effective strategy to enhance operational efficiency in experiments related to microfiltration or similar processes.

Table 5. Relative mean deviation (RMD).

Membrane (μm)	Pressure (bar)	D.R.M (%)
0.22	1	31.05
3.00	1	64.47
0.22	2	16.26
3.00	2	18.64

The reevaluation of manual micelle revealed variations in the number of micelles per volume, highlighting the inherent limitations of visual counting performed by the human eye through the Neubauer chamber. These discrepancies can be attributed to factors for example visual fatigue. The implementation of an automatic counting application not only overcomes these limitations, but also represents a substantial improvement. Automation provides precision and consistency, reducing the influence of human errors and enabling a more efficient analysis. Thus, the transition to the use of automatic applications not only optimizes the micelle counting process but also strengthens the reliability and quality of the obtained data.

Automatic counting revealed a higher quantity of micelles compared to manual counting, indicating greater sensitivity in micelle detection. These differences can have significant implications in assessing the permeate quality, underscoring the importance of carefully choosing the counting method to obtain accurate and reliable results. The implementation of the ContLab app during the fermentation process is necessary to reduce recurrent errors made manually by experts, which require considerable physical effort and concentration, thus minimizing production costs and risks.

4. CONCLUSION

The present work introduces an innovative mobile application that performs automatic counting of particles in liquid solution, arranged in Neubauer or glass slide chambers, based on digital image processing. Unlike other related works that focused on specific particles (such as red blood cells), the ContLab App targets a broad spectrum of particle sizes, ranging from 0.05 μm to 50 μm , i.e., the operating range of the microfiltration process and the upper limit of ultrafiltration. Particles are counted in all quadrants of the Neubauer chamber, where lens distortion issues are corrected for the accurate automatic image processing. The instantaneous measurement of micelles number in the permeate plays a crucial role in assessing the need for a new broth recirculation, essential for the proper formation of a micelle layer on the membrane. This technique provides an efficient approach for researchers, allowing real-time assessments and thus significantly optimizing time utilization. In contrast, manual counting would require hours.

There is a difference between manual and automatic counting, where there has been an improvement with automatic counting of up to 36 micelles/ mm^3 of permeate, indicating greater reliability in sample analysis when employing this innovation. In a sampling universe of permeate where the maximum counting was 133 micelles/ mm^3 . Furthermore, particle counting performed by the present app is rapid. Considering the sample is already positioned on the microscope, and the application is ready for use, the analysis and results are immediate. Additionally, the ContLab app is ready for use.

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